

1 **Opposite effects of lateralised transcranial alpha versus gamma stimulation on spatial**
2 **attention**

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18 **Abstract**

19 Spatial attention relatively increases the power of neural 10-Hz alpha oscillations in the hemisphere
20 ipsilateral to attention. The functional roles of lateralised oscillations for attention are unclear. Here,
21 20 human participants performed a dichotic listening task under continuous transcranial
22 alternating current stimulation (tACS) at alpha (10 Hz, vs sham) or gamma (47 Hz, vs sham)
23 frequency, targeting left temporo-parietal cortex. Participants attended to four spoken numbers
24 presented to one ear, while ignoring numbers on the other ear. As predicted, we found that alpha-
25 tACS contralateral to the attended ear decreased recall of attended targets. Notably, gamma-tACS
26 reversed the effect. Results provide a proof of concept that externally amplified oscillations can
27 enhance spatial attention and facilitate attentional selection of speech. Furthermore, opposite
28 effects of alpha versus gamma oscillations support the view that, across modalities, states of high
29 alpha are incommensurate with active neural processing as reflected by states of high gamma.

30 **Introduction**

31 When humans focus attention to one location in space, neural oscillatory alpha power (~10 Hz)
32 relatively increases in sensory areas in the hemisphere ipsilateral to the focus of attention and
33 decreases in the contralateral hemisphere (1-3). The prevailing functional interpretation is that
34 high ipsilateral alpha power inhibits cortical activity in the hemisphere processing the unattended
35 side of space, which agrees with the functional inhibition theory of alpha oscillations (4, 5). This
36 view receives further support by studies showing that gamma power (>40 Hz), which reflects active
37 cortical processing (6) and correlates negatively with alpha power (7), lateralises in the opposite
38 way compared to alpha power during spatial attention (8-10). In the present combined behavioural
39 and tACS (transcranial alternating current stimulation) study, we test whether lateralised alpha and
40 gamma oscillations are just epiphenomena of attention or whether they, when externally
41 amplified, modulate accuracy of auditory spatial attention to speech.

42 In the visual modality, rhythmic transcranial magnetic stimulation (rTMS) at alpha frequency
43 applied to one hemisphere has been shown to enhance perception (11) and to improve memory
44 for targets ipsilateral to the stimulated hemisphere (12, for a review of TMS effects on visuospatial
45 attention, see 13). In audition, however, the existence of an *auditory alpha rhythm* (14) and
46 functional roles thereof are notoriously more challenging to assess experimentally (15, 16). Also,
47 the link between the amplitude of lateralised auditory alpha oscillations and spatial attention is
48 purely correlational so far: In a recent magnetoencephalography (MEG) study (17), we found that
49 stronger temporally modulated alpha lateralisation (i.e., high ipsi- and low contralateral alpha
50 power) predicted better recall of attended speech in a dichotic listening task. Here, we use the
51 same task and aim to boost participants' endogenous neural oscillations using tACS to increase the
52 amplitude of alpha or gamma oscillations (see e.g., 18, 19, 20) in a superior temporal/inferior
53 parietal cortex region in the left hemisphere. This region was found to exhibit marked and directly
54 performance-related alpha lateralisation during this task (17).

55 If lateralised oscillatory power were a mere *correlate* or epiphenomenon of neural processes
56 that instantiate attention, alpha- and gamma-tACS should not affect accuracy of spatial attention.
57 However, our findings demonstrate that left hemispheric alpha- versus gamma-tACS do modulate
58 oppositely the recall of attended speech on the left versus right side. This is evidence that
59 lateralised oscillations are a functionally significant *substrate* of spatial attention.

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61 **Results & Discussion**

62 In a dichotic listening task, $n = 20$ participants attended to four spoken numbers presented to one
63 ear, while they ignored four numbers presented simultaneously to the other ear. In the end of each
64 trial, participants had the task to select the four numbers presented to the to-be-attended side
65 from a visually presented number pad (Fig. 1A). This paradigm has been shown to induce robust

66 lateralisation of neural oscillations, with relative high alpha power in auditory and parietal cortex
 67 regions in the hemisphere ipsi- versus contralateral to the focus of attention (Fig. 1B, left; 17). Here,
 68 we aimed at increasing the amplitude of participants' lateralised oscillations during dichotic
 69 listening using left-hemispheric tACS at alpha (10 Hz) or gamma (47.1 Hz) frequency.
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 72 **Figure 1.** (A) Dichotic listening task. A cue tone on one ear (left in this example) indicated the to-be-attended side on this
 73 trial. Four spoken numbers were presented to the left ear, and four different (same-talker) numbers to the right ear. The
 74 task was to select the four to-be-attended numbers (i.e., targets) from a visually presented number pad shown after the
 75 end of auditory stimulation. Green edges, which were not shown to participants, indicate correct responses on this trial.
 76 (B, left) Topography and brain surfaces show hemispheric lateralisation of alpha power (8–12 Hz) during the presentation
 77 of numbers, obtained in a previous magnetoencephalography (MEG) study using the same task (17) by contrasting
 78 attend-left versus attend-right trials: (attend-left–attend-right) / (attend-left+attend-right). Overlays on brain surfaces
 79 are masked at $p = 0.05$; uncorrected. (B, right) Simulation of current densities emitted by our tACS stimulation setup as
 80 calculated in SimNIBS (21). Stimulation was intended to target temporo-parietal regions (around target region pSTG) in
 81 the left hemisphere. (C) The experiment was divided in two sessions, which took part on different days. In each session,
 82 participants first performed a short training, followed by a sham run of the experiment without tACS stimulation, a short
 83 break, and finally another run of the experiment under continuous tACS stimulation lasting 25 min (alpha session: 10 Hz;
 84 gamma session: 47.1 Hz). (D) tACS stimulation was applied to electrodes TP7 and FC5 (black dots on topographies and in
 85 B, right). Alpha- versus gamma-tACS were expected to induce differential patterns of increasing (upward pointing
 86 arrows) and decreasing accuracy (downward pointing arrows) in attend-left/-right trials (see text for details).
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89 In humans, left auditory cortex regions receive input predominantly from the right ear and vice
 90 versa for right auditory cortex (22, 23). Therefore, our tACS setup, which targeted primarily left
 91 auditory and parietal regions (Fig. 1B, right), was expected to affect neural processing of the right-
 92 ear input in a highly predictable way (Fig. 1D): Left-hemispheric alpha-tACS should inhibit neural
 93 processing of the right-ear input, leading to reduced accuracy in attend-right but enhanced
 94 accuracy in attend-left trials. Contrary, left-hemispheric gamma-tACS should facilitate neural
 95 processing of the right-ear input, leading to enhanced accuracy in attend-right but reduced
 96 accuracy in attend-left trials.

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98 **Right-ear advantage in the dichotic listening task.** For statistical analyses, we used linear mixed-
99 effects models to regress the proportion of correctly recalled digits in each trial on the predictor
100 variables session (alpha vs gamma), stimulation (sham vs tACS), and to-be-attended side (left vs
101 right). As expected for dichotic listening, proportion correct was higher for attend-right than
102 attend-left trials ($b = 0.075$; $F_{1,8773} = 115.15$; $p < 0.001$). This demonstrates the well-known right-ear
103 advantage (REA; 24), which rests on structural (25), but also attentional hemispheric asymmetries
104 (26).

105 Since the right-ear advantage in dichotic listening tasks is known to be of limited test-retest
106 reliability in the individual (27, 28), we included a sham run immediately before the tACS run in
107 each experimental session (see Fig. 1C). Thus, tACS effects could be quantified by contrasting each
108 participants' tACS run with the sham run of the respective session.

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Figure 2. Effects of left-hemispheric tACS on behaviour in the dichotic listening task. (A) Results of the alpha session (10-Hz stimulation). Bars and errorbars show mean ± 1 between-subject SEM of proportion correct responses in the dichotic listening task for attend-left and attend-right trials. The line plot shows the tACS effect (10-Hz tACS-Sham; logit-transformed) for $n = 20$ individual participants (thin lines), bold line shows average across participants. (B) Same as A but for the gamma session (47.1-Hz tACS).

119 **Alpha- and gamma-tACS differentially modulate auditory spatial attention.** Most importantly,
120 and directly in line with our hypotheses (Fig. 1D), the session \times stimulation \times to-be-attended side
121 interaction was significant ($b = 0.062$; $F_{1,8773} = 11.68$; $p < 0.001$). Compared to sham, left-hemispheric
122 alpha-tACS enhanced the proportion correct in attend-left trials but decreased the proportion
123 correct in attend-right trials (Fig. 2A; stimulation \times to-be-attended side interaction: $b = -0.024$; $F_{1,4377} = 3.57$; $p = 0.059$), while the pattern of results precisely reversed for gamma-tACS (Fig. 2B;
124 stimulation \times to-be-attended side interaction: $b = 0.038$; $F_{1,4377} = 8.83$; $p = 0.003$).

126 So far, electric stimulation studies targeting one hemisphere have found shifts of visuo-spatial
127 attention in case of transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS; 29, 30), whereas tACS at alpha
128 frequency has produced inconclusive (31) or non-replicable results (32). For auditory spatial
129 processing, one study aimed at modulating the right-ear advantage using tDCS applied to either

130 the left or right hemisphere during dichotic listening but did not observe hemisphere-specific
131 performance modulations (33). To the contrary, the opposing effects of left-hemispheric alpha-
132 versus gamma-tACS observed here show that externally amplified lateralised oscillations modulate
133 the focus of auditory attention in a frequency-specific way: tACS-increased alpha oscillations
134 inhibit, while tACS-increased gamma oscillations facilitate, the attentional selection of speech
135 presented contralateral to the stimulated hemisphere. Thus, both lateralised alpha and gamma
136 oscillations exert a functional relevance in auditory spatial attention.

137 Our participants were stimulated continuously for 25 minutes and, since the trial timing was not
138 fixed but depended on a participant's response speed, the onsets of auditory events (cue tone and
139 numbers) were randomly distributed across the cycle of the stimulated alpha or gamma oscillation.
140 Thus, whereas previous research found phase effects of alpha-tACS on auditory perception (e.g.,
141 34), the present study demonstrates that tACS modulates spatial attention to auditory events
142 which are non-phase-locked to the stimulated oscillation.

143 Based on the theoretically proposed (e.g., 4) and empirically observed opposing roles of
144 inhibitory alpha and facilitatory gamma power for spatial attention (e.g., 35), we expected
145 hemispheric gamma-tACS to reverse the effect of alpha-tACS. Our results confirm this. Previous
146 tACS studies have shown that high-frequency random noise stimulation (100–640 Hz) targeting
147 auditory cortex enhanced auditory responses in the EEG (36) and improved auditory gap-detection
148 performance (37). Together with these studies, our results support the view that gamma-tACS can
149 facilitate auditory processing and thus affects auditory spatial attention inversely compared to
150 tACS-entrained inhibitory alpha oscillations.

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152 **Left-hemispheric tACS affects attend-right trials.** Separate analyses of attend-left and attend-
153 right trials revealed that the session (alpha vs gamma) \times stimulation (tACS vs sham) interaction was
154 significant for attend-right trials ($b = 0.051$; $F_{1, 4377} = 17.41$; $p < 0.001$) but not for attend-left trials ($b =$
155 -0.011 ; $F_{1, 4377} = 0.67$; $p = 0.413$). We assume that this is due to our left-hemispheric locus of
156 stimulation, which, due to the contralateral organization of the human auditory system, modulated
157 auditory processing of task-relevant target speech in attend-right trials but processing of task-
158 irrelevant distractor speech in attend-left trials (see Fig. 1D). Recall accuracy in the dichotic listening
159 task likely depends more on attending to target speech, and hinges only indirectly on ignoring the
160 distractor (for a similar argument, see 38). Thus, the impact of tACS-increased oscillations of either
161 frequency on target speech (in attend-right trials) was larger than the impact of tACS-increased
162 oscillations on distractor speech (in attend-left trials).

163 Note that stronger effects of left-hemispheric alpha- and gamma-tACS in attend-right trials
164 indirectly support the feasibility of our stimulation setup in targeting primarily regions in the left
165 hemisphere. In theory, right- instead of left-hemispheric tACS in our dichotic listening task should

166 induce stronger performance modulations in attend-left trials. But functional asymmetries of left
167 versus right auditory cortex regions could further complicate this reasoning (39, 40).

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169 **Functional roles of lateralised alpha and gamma oscillations.** The pattern of our results is in
170 striking accordance with the hypothesised roles of lateralised inhibitory alpha and facilitatory
171 gamma oscillations for spatial attention (Fig. 1D). It is important to note, however, that even
172 experiments employing perturbation techniques such as tACS allow only limited causal inference
173 (41). For instance, it might be that tACS-increased lateralised alpha oscillations causally inhibit
174 neural processing in the stimulated brain regions, whereas tACS-increased gamma oscillations are
175 causally ineffective by themselves but instead provide a means to decrease the power of causally
176 effective alpha oscillations (for an effect of gamma-tACS on alpha oscillations, see 42).

177 Furthermore, our results do not reveal at which level of auditory processing tACS-increased
178 alpha and gamma oscillations are effective. In line with the predominant views on the functional
179 roles of neural oscillations (e.g., 43), it is reasonable to assume that alpha-tACS affects behaviour
180 through inhibition of (top-down) attention to one side of space whereas gamma-tACS affects
181 behaviour through facilitation of neural (bottom-up) encoding (see e.g., 10) of auditory stimuli in
182 left versus right auditory cortex. Alternatively, alpha- and gamma-tACS might affect the same
183 neural processes but in opposite direction, but this view is somewhat weakened by the present
184 data: the effects of alpha- and gamma-tACS on the recall of target numbers (i.e., tACS–sham, logit
185 transformed) were not significantly negatively correlated (attend-left trials: $r = 0.19$; $p = 0.427$;
186 attend-right trials: $r = 0.02$; $p = 0.938$). Combining brain stimulation, neuroimaging and behavioural
187 measures should test these alternative explanations in future studies (44).

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189 **Conclusions.** Lateralised neural oscillations across the cerebral hemispheres are a well-known
190 signature of spatial attention. Here, we show that increased lateralised alpha and gamma
191 oscillations using transcranial alternating current stimulation hold the power to modulate spatial
192 attention to one of the most important sensory signals in human environments, that is, speech. In
193 agreement with prevailing views on alpha and gamma oscillations, our results support the
194 functional relevance of these regimes of neural oscillations for auditory spatial attention: The
195 attentional selection of speech presented to the left or right side is inhibited when alpha power
196 increases in the contralateral hemisphere (and vice versa for gamma power).

197 **Materials and Methods**

198 **Participants.** Twenty young healthy participants (19–31 years, 10 females) with no history of
199 neurological or psychiatric disorders participated. One participant was not fully right handed
200 (laterality quotient of 20 on a scale from –100 (left handed) to +100 (right handed)) according to
201 the Edinburgh inventory (45). Two participants were non-German native speakers but of sufficient
202 German language proficiency to perform the dichotic listening task. Experimental procedures were
203 approved by the local ethics committee of the University of Oldenburg (Kommission für
204 Forschungsfolgenabschätzung und Ethik).

205 **Auditory stimuli.** We used German, female-voiced 4-syllable numbers from previous studies (46,
206 47). Recordings of spoken numbers from 21 to 99 (excluding integer multiples of 10) with a
207 sampling rate of 44.1 kHz were shortened in Praat (version 6.0.14) by a factor of 0.85, resulting in a
208 mean (\pm SD) number duration of 0.96 s (\pm 0.05 s). We determined the perceptual center (P-center) of
209 each number (48) as the time point when the number signal's broad-band envelope (15-Hz
210 lowpass-filtered modulus of the Hilbert transform) reached 50% of the first syllable's peak
211 amplitude. In the following, the onset of a number refers to its perceptual center. For the spatial
212 cue, we used a monaural 1000-Hz sine tone of 500-ms duration.

213 **Dichotic listening task.** The dichotic listening task was a slightly speeded version of a task used
214 previously (17). For each trial, eight different numbers were selected randomly from the pool of all
215 numbers; four to-be-presented to the left, the other four to-be-presented simultaneously to the
216 right ear. For simultaneously presented numbers on the left and right ear, perceptual centers were
217 temporally aligned and numbers were distinct in their first and second digit (e.g., co-occurrences of
218 "35" and "37" or "81" and "21" were avoided).

219 Each trial started with the presentation of the cue (to one ear) to indicate whether participants
220 had to attend to the left or right in this trial. The cue was followed (after 500 ms) simultaneously by
221 four spoken numbers presented to the left ear and four different numbers to the right ear (Fig. 1A).
222 The onset-to-onset time interval of two subsequent numbers was 1.25 s. Presentation of acoustic
223 stimuli (cue and numbers) took on average (\pm SD) 5.66 s (\pm 0.04). Finally, cue tone and spoken
224 numbers were embedded in continuous background noise (white noise; +10 dB SNR). Cue tone
225 and background noise had 50-ms linear onset and offset ramps.

226 Approximately 0.5 s (jittered 0.3 – 0.7 s) after the offset of the last two simultaneous numbers a
227 response screen was shown that contained 12 numbers (four from the to-be-attended side, four
228 from the to-be-ignored side, and four random numbers not presented on any side). Participants
229 were asked to use a mouse to select the four numbers that appeared on the to-be-attended side in
230 any order. Numbers on the response screen were presented in either ascending or descending
231 order (randomised from trial to trial) to prevent motor preparation during a trial. After selection of
232 four numbers, the next trial started automatically (after approximately 1 s, randomly jittered 0.8 –

233 1.2 s). Auditory materials were presented via Sennheiser HD 25-1 II headphones. In one run of the
234 experiment a participant performed 110 trials, which took on average 26'31" ($\pm 2'4"$ SD) to
235 complete. Trial order was fully randomised with the constraint that the spatial cue appeared on the
236 left side in half of the trials in each run.

237 **tACS stimulation.** We used a lateralised tACS stimulation setup, which was designed to target left-
238 hemispheric posterior superior temporal gyrus (pSTG) and surrounding auditory and parietal
239 cortex regions. Round electrodes of 3 cm diameter were placed at sites FC5 and TP7 according to
240 the international 10-10 system. Electrode impedance was kept below 10 k Ω . The stimulator (DC
241 stimulator plus, Eldith, 419 NeuroConn, Ilmenau, Germany) emitted a sinusoidal alternating current
242 with no DC offset at frequencies of either 10 Hz (alpha) or 47.1 Hz (gamma) at a strength of 1 mA
243 (milliampere) peak-to-peak. The gamma stimulation frequency of 47.1 Hz was chosen to not match
244 a multiple (i.e., harmonic) of the alpha frequency. Stimulation amplitude was ramped up and down
245 linearly over 20 or 94.2 cycles (2 Sec) for 10 Hz and 47.1 Hz stimulation frequencies, respectively.
246 Overall tACS was applied continuously for 25 minutes between the two ramping periods.

247 For sham stimulation, the tACS setup was the same as for alpha and gamma stimulation, except
248 that the stimulation consisted only of the ramping periods at the beginning and subsequently
249 remained off for the rest of the run.

250 **Procedure.** In total, each participant performed four runs of the dichotic listening task (resulting in
251 $4 \times 110 = 440$ trials per participant), separated in two sessions taking place on different days: alpha
252 session (sham run & alpha-tACS run) and gamma session (sham run & gamma-tACS run). Session
253 order (alpha-->gamma vs gamma--> alpha) was balanced across participants and the two sessions
254 were separated by 5–14 days (average: 7.58 days). Each session started with a short training
255 (approx. 5 min) to familiarise the participant with the task procedure. Next, participants performed
256 the sham run, followed by a short break and the alpha/gamma-tACS stimulation run. Within each
257 session the sham run was tested first in order to avoid possible confounds of tACS after-effects,
258 which are known to outlast the duration of stimulation considerably (49, 50).

259 **Statistical analyses.** The major dependent measure in the present study was the proportion of
260 correctly recalled numbers on attend-left versus attend-right trials. On each trial participants
261 selected four numbers from the response screen, resulting in five possible proportions of correctly
262 recalled numbers: 1 (four out of four), 0.75 (three out of four), 0.5 (two out of four), 0.25 (one out of
263 four), 0 (zero out of four).

264 The study implemented a 2 (session: alpha vs gamma) \times 2 (stimulation: sham vs tACS) \times 2 (to-
265 be-attended side: left vs right) within-subject design. For the statistical analysis we fitted linear
266 mixed-effects models using the *lme4* package for R (version 2017-03-06) and Rstudio (version
267 1.0.136). In essence, participants' single-trial data were used to model the response variable
268 proportion correct on the three predictors. To obtain *p*-values for predictors (51), we used the

269 *anova* function using Satterthwaite approximation implemented in the *lmerTest* package. These *p*-
270 values were also compared to *p*-values obtained with the *mixed* function using parametric
271 bootstrapping implemented in the *afex* package, which yielded almost identical results.

272 For visualization of group data (bar graphs in Fig. 2), we averaged the proportion correct for
273 each experimental condition. For visualization of single-subject data (line graphs in Fig. 2), we
274 logit-transformed the proportion correct data for each subject and condition (52), followed by
275 calculation of the tACS effect (tACS–sham), separately for the alpha and gamma session.

276 **Side effects of tACS.** According to questionnaires answered in the end of each session (alpha &
277 gamma), the side effects reported by most of our 20 participants were tingling (alpha: 18; gamma:
278 15), difficulty in concentration (alpha: 17; gamma: 15), and tiredness (alpha: 12; gamma: 10).
279 However, only a subset of participants attributed these side effects to the tACS stimulation
280 (tingling, alpha: 13, gamma: 12; difficulty in concentration, alpha: 7, gamma: 6; tiredness, alpha: 5,
281 gamma: 4). Intensities of these side effects (rated on a scale from 0 = 'no' to 4 = 'strong') did not
282 differ between alpha and gamma sessions (Wilcoxon signed rank tests; all $p > 0.1$).

283 Participants were also asked in the end of each session to indicate for individual runs of a
284 session (sham & tACS) whether they think they were stimulated. For the alpha session, 7
285 participants reported stimulation during sham and 12 during tACS (McNemar test; $p = 0.18$). For the
286 gamma session, 6 participants reported stimulation during sham and 15 during tACS ($p = 0.012$).
287 Stronger sensation of stimulation in the gamma session might explain a change in overall
288 performance but not our specific hypothesised response patterns (i.e., differential performance
289 modulation in attend-left versus attend-right trials; see Fig. 1D). We thus consider these side effects
290 uncritical to the results of the present study.

291 **Statistical control analyses.** The major result of this study was the significant session \times
292 stimulation \times to-be-attended side interaction, obtained via mixed-effects linear regression analysis.
293 We used two additional linear mixed-effects models to confirm the robustness of this interaction.
294 First, this interaction remained significant when we controlled for session order (alpha-->gamma vs
295 gamma-->alpha; $b = 0.062$; $F_{1, 8766} = 11.71$; $p < 0.001$) and laterality quotient ($b = 0.062$; $F_{1, 8766} =$
296 11.72 ; $p < 0.001$), assessed by the Edinburgh handedness questionnaire (45).

297 Second, since non-normality of residuals is a potential confound in linear regression, we
298 backed-up our statistical analysis using Poisson regression to model the number of errors on each
299 trial (0, 1, 2, 3, or 4), which confirmed the significant right-ear advantage ($b = -0.003$; $F_1 = 70.07$; $p <$
300 0.001) and session \times stimulation \times to-be-attended side interaction ($b = -0.002$; $F_1 = 7.94$; $p = 0.005$).
301 Third, in addition to the single-trial mixed effects approach used in the present study, we also
302 performed a traditional repeated-measures ANOVA on the average proportion of correctly recalled
303 numbers in each condition, which also revealed a significant right-ear advantage ($F_{1, 19} = 13.23$; $p =$

304 0.002; $\eta^2_p = 0.41$) and session \times stimulation \times to-be-attended side interaction ($F_{1,19} = 7.63$; $p = 0.012$;
305 $\eta^2_p = 0.29$).

306 Furthermore, it is critical in the present study to control for possible changes in proportion
307 correct across the time of an experimental run, for three reasons: First, our ethics approval allowed
308 25 min of continuous tACS stimulation, but some participants required >25 min to complete a run
309 of the experiment (mean run duration $\pm 1SD$; alpha session, sham: 27'14" \pm 2'53", tACS: 26'25"
310 \pm 3'11"; gamma session, sham: 26'48" \pm 2'59", tACS: 25'37" \pm 3'05"). Second, in each session, we first
311 measured the sham run followed by the tACS stimulation run, leading to significantly faster
312 completion of tACS compared to sham runs (repeated-measures ANOVA; $F_{1,19} = 13.81$; $p = 0.001$; η^2_p
313 $= 0.42$). Third, it has been speculated that during longer time periods of continuous lateralised tACS
314 stimulation, the applied current would initially reach target areas and later spread to non-target
315 areas in the contralateral hemisphere, which could confound effects of lateralised tACS (31). For
316 these reasons, we conducted two additional linear regressions to control for single-trial offset
317 times (measured in milliseconds relative to the offset of the ramp-up of the stimulation amplitude
318 in the beginning of each run) and stimulation offset, coded 0 for all trials completed within the first
319 25 min and 1 for all trials completed thereafter. Importantly, the session \times stimulation \times to-be-
320 attended side interaction was significant when we controlled for single-trial offset time ($b = 0.063$;
321 $F_{1,8766} = 12.12$; $p < 0.001$) as well as stimulation offset ($b = 0.06$; $F_{1,8766} = 5.64$; $p = 0.018$). Furthermore,
322 single-trial offset time and stimulation offset did not exhibit main or interaction effects on
323 proportion correct (all $p > 0.05$).

324 **Effect sizes.** Since there are no standard effect size measures for individual predictors and their
325 interactions in linear mixed models, we report the unstandardized coefficient (b), which
326 corresponds to the estimated change in the dependent variable (proportion correctly recalled
327 numbers) when the predictor increases by one level. For repeated-measures ANOVAs, we report
328 partial eta squared (η^2_p).

329

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A

Left ear: "24" "97" "52" "33"
 Right ear: "36" "88" "31" "79"

99	97	88	79
71	68	52	42
36	33	31	24

— Target

B

C

Alpha session

Gamma session

D

A

B

